

A Simple Relation Between Latent Heat of Vaporization and Temperature

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The latent heats of vaporization (l_v) have been calculated at different temperatures (T) using the accurate form of Clapeyron equation, for methane, carbon tetrachloride, acetylene, ethylene, cyclohexane, benzene, chlorobenzene, *n*-heptane, *n*-octane, water, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, and diethylamine all from the normal boiling points to the critical temperatures (T_c). A number of relations between l_v and T has been tried. The plot of $\log l_v$ against $\log (T_c - T)$ is surprisingly straight except within five degrees of T_c , and enables us to calculate l_v at any temperature, from an equation of the form $\log l_v = m \log (T_c - T) + c$. The constants m and c are different for different liquids and have been tabulated.

ATTEMPTS have been made to find a relation between l_v and T . Watson¹ used

$$\frac{l_{v_2}}{l_{v_1}} = \left(\frac{T_c - T_2}{T_c - T_1} \right)^{0.88} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

which enables l_{v_2} at T_2 to be calculated if l_{v_1} at T_1 is known. The need exists to connect l_v with T independent of another known pair. Rules of Trouton² or Giacalone³ refer to l_v at normal boiling point only and even for that the nature of approximation is well known. l_v is accurately calculated from the equation

$$\left(\frac{dP}{dT} \right)_v = \left(\frac{\Delta S}{\Delta V} \right)_T; \quad \frac{l_v}{T} = \Delta S \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

We could have obtained a theoretical equation between l_v and T if $\left(\frac{dP}{dT} \right)_v$ and ΔV were related to T by theory. No simple theory exists for these purposes so that at present we can search for an empirical relation only between the two. To do so we must find accurate values of l_v at short temperature intervals and use the resulting graph to find an empirical equation.

Data and Calculations

We have used the vapour pressure, temperature and the orthobaric densities (of liquids and vapours) from Lange⁴. The data of water are from Gerasimov⁵. l_v has been calculated with the help of the equation $l_v = \frac{dP}{dT} \cdot T (v_g - v_l)$ where v_g , v_l are

specific volumes of the gas (vapour) and the liquid. The results of calculation are given in Table 1. The plot of l_v against T gives smooth graphs rising

towards the lower temperatures. To judge whether they tend to a parabola or a hyperbola, $\log l_v$ was plotted against $\log T$ on the one hand and $\frac{T_c - T}{l_v}$ against $(T_c - T)$ on the other. $(T_c - T)$ was used in place of T to bring the curves in the first quadrant. In neither case did we get lines which maintained their slopes constant throughout.

Calculations show that l_v tends towards zero at T_c . We therefore investigated the variation of l_v with $(T_c - T)$. l_v was of course not proportional to $(T_c - T)$, but the plots of $\log l_v$ against $\log (T_c - T)$ gave the graphs shown in Fig. 1. The graphs are surprisingly straight. If there are deviations of the experimental points from the graphs, they are not seen above $\log (T_c - T) = 0.7$ which means that deviations are mostly confined to within five degrees of

T_c . The $\log (T_c - T)$ scale is the same for all curves. The graphs have been shifted vertically according to need to accommodate them in the same figure. Graphs for methane, *n*-octane, chlorobenzene and water are not shown.

In order to find specific linear equations between l_v and $(T_c - T)$ for each substance the corresponding slopes and intercepts in Fig. 1 were determined. They are tabulated in Table 2.

The l_v , T data for water have been directly taken from Gerasimov and appear to be calorimetrically measured values. They are quoted below, in rounded figures.

$T^\circ\text{K}$	273	293	323	373	473	573	623	643	647
l_v , cal/g	595	584	568	539	463	335	213	109	35

TABLE 1—CALCULATIONS OF l_v FOR DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE RANGES

Carbon tetrachloride $T_c = 556.1^\circ\text{K}$				Cyclohexane $T_c = 558^\circ\text{K}$			
1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Mean T $^\circ\text{K}$	dP/dT atm/ $^\circ\text{K}$	$(v_g - v_l)$ cc/g	l_v cal/g				
358	.0360	143.76	44.85	358	.0331	302.59	87.07
368	.0454	110.35	44.22	368	.0409	232.22	84.68
378	.0557	86.01	43.87	378	.0504	179.96	82.97
388	.0671	67.94	42.81	388	.0596	140.39	78.56
398	.0802	54.27	41.93	398	.0720	111.01	76.98
408	.0954	43.77	41.23	408	.0878	89.14	77.27
418	.1092	35.69	39.44	418	.1033	71.79	75.02
428	.1290	29.38	39.25	428	.1185	58.29	71.53
438	.1454	25.30	39.01	438	.1388	...	...
448	.1653	21.54	38.60	448	.1566	...	...
458	.1870	17.13	35.50	458	.1774	32.98	64.84
468	.2130	14.27	34.50	468	.1970	27.22	60.74
478	.2400	12.44	34.53	478	.2230	22.51	58.07
488	.2670	10.12	31.91	488	.2450	18.67	54.00
498	.2990	7.95	28.65	498	.2790	15.78	53.06
508	.334	6.53	26.81	508	.3070	13.05	49.22
518	.370	5.29	24.48	518	.3370	10.26	43.32
528	.411	4.153	21.80	528	.3800	8.00	38.33
538	.456	2.939	17.46	538	.4260	5.82	32.23
548	.500	1.876	12.44	548	.4700	2.37	14.74
554.6	.584	0.730	1.80				

(Table 1 Contd.)

Methane $T_c=191^\circ\text{K}$							
1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
112	.0866	525.416	128.60	158	.599	44.244	101.38
118	.122	375.794	130.92	168	.787	27.550	88.15
128	.203	199.230	125.28	178	1.02	16.083	70.66
138	.307	115.559	118.48	186.9	1.253	5.616	31.84
148	.439	70.468	110.80				
Methyl alcohol $T_c=513^\circ\text{K}$							
340	.0415	749.1262	256.0615	428	.3540	55.5220	203.5764
348	.0544	579.8700	265.6588	438	.4290	43.2642	193.9807
358	.0730	410.5520	259.6509	448	.5010	33.8401	183.8073
368	.0958	296.1107	252.6288	458	.5880	26.4598	172.4427
378	.1236	217.0955	245.4576	468	.6850	20.5503	159.4300
388	.1567	161.5775	237.7391	478	.7950	15.6641	144.0509
398	.1958	121.8558	229.8099	488	.9150	11.4862	124.1174
408	.2417	92.9874	221.7904	498	1.0490	7.8487	99.2243
418	.2940	71.6058	212.9547	508	1.1830	3.0785	44.7716
Ethyl alcohol $T_c=516^\circ\text{K}$							
352	.0406	589.0273	203.8001	438	.3220	44.9352	153.3670
358	.0493	485.9863	207.5723	448	.383	34.8450	144.6380
368	.0666	341.0620	202.2883	458	.450	26.9455	134.3939
378	.0879	243.9237	196.1327	468	.5260	20.6593	123.0700
388	.1360	177.4380	189.2658	478	.6110	15.6281	110.4563
398	.1442	131.8419	183.1121	488	.7070	11.5349	96.3090
408	.1801	99.2248	176.4450	498	.8150	8.1527	80.0763
418	.2214	75.4804	169.0454	508	.9390	4.9147	56.7338
428	.2690	58.1377	161.9829	514.5	1.0260	1.6083	20.5454
<i>n</i> -propyl alcohol $T_c=536.7^\circ\text{K}$							
371.7	.0385	462.5946	160.2025	458	.2670	38.9389	113.4571
378	.0477	376.1149	164.1142	468	.3110	30.2319	106.4347
388	.0631	267.7211	158.6204	478	.3600	24.3497	101.4003
398	.0814	194.0935	152.1717	488	.4110	19.1112	92.7609
408	.1033	141.8087	144.6368	498	.4690	14.2275	80.4167
418	.1286	106.3068	138.2909	508	.5310	10.6610	69.5940
428	.1374	81.9023	116.5580	518	.5980	7.6470	57.3241
438	.1902	62.9477	126.9053	528	.6720	4.9575	42.5678
448	.2263	48.9011	119.9766	534.9	.7919	1.8251	13.6701
Benzene $T_c=562^\circ\text{K}$							
368	.0431	243.9092	93.6430	468	.2110	29.3662	70.1765
378	.0533	188.3953	91.8553	478	.2370	24.4266	66.9660
388	.0644	146.9778	88.3760	488	.2730	20.2599	65.3183
398	.0776	115.7074	86.4811	498	.3010	16.6991	60.5765
408	.0920	93.1235	84.5907	508	.3330	13.6866	56.0296
418	.1070	75.7391	81.9777	518	.3750	11.1048	52.2020
428	.1270	62.2441	81.8768	528	.4150	8.8351	46.8499
438	.1430	51.4194	77.9386	538	.4600	6.7604	40.4881
448	.1630	42.5698	75.2285	548	.5200	4.7862	33.0058
458	.1870	35.3950	73.3600	557.5	.5440	1.9043	13.9764
Chlorobenzene $T_c=632.2^\circ\text{K}$							
418	.0354	207.840	74.430	488	.1085	49.844	63.867
428	.0430	165.070	73.518	498	.1281	41.886	62.140
438	.0506	131.990	70.791	508	.1394	35.166	60.264
448	.0592	107.470	68.976	518	.1604	29.581	59.478
458	.0693	87.930	68.025	528	.1820	25.232	58.677
468	.0816	71.004	66.543	538	.2030	20.890	55.212
478	.0934	59.610	54.403	587.6	.3300	9.524	44.692

TABLE 2—CONSTANTS OF THE LINEAR EQUATION

Substance	$T_c^\circ\text{K}$	c	m	Substance	$T_c^\circ\text{K}$	c	m
MeOH	513	1.540	0.4000	<i>n</i> -octane	570	0.955	0.4061
EtOH	516	1.340	0.4440	CCl_4	556	0.800	0.3750
<i>n</i> -PrOH	536.7	1.150	0.4773	Benzene	562	1.070	0.3909
Water	647	1.825	0.3691	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$	632	1.235	0.2874
Methane	191	1.490	0.3981	Cyclohexane	558	1.055	0.3841
Ethane	305	1.320	0.3609	Diethylamine	496	1.085	0.4528
Acetylene	309	1.390	0.4163	Acetone	508	1.125	0.4555
Ethylene	283	1.425	0.3140	Acetic acid	595	1.190	0.3739
<i>n</i> -heptane	543	0.950	0.4166				

The Linear Relation :

The relation between l_c and $(T_c - T)$ may be therefore set down to $\log l_v = m \log (T_c - T) + c$. From two such equations for conditions 2 and 1 one

gets by subtraction, $\log \frac{l_{v2}}{l_{v1}} = m \log \left(\frac{T_c - T_2}{T_c - T_1} \right)$ which

is Watson's equation in logarithmic form. However, the constant m does not turn out to be always 0.38 as set down by him. Methane, ethylene and chlorobenzene give low values. Higher values are more frequent, e.g., for acetone, diethylamine, ethyl and *n*-propyl alcohols. Consequently, when we re-calculated the ratio of $\frac{l_{v2}}{l_{v1}}$ for different pairs of

mean temperatures according to Watson's formula and compared them with directly calculated l_{v2}/l_{v1} (Clapeyron equation) we found large differences in these cases. Thus, in the case of *n*-propyl alcohol differences were observed amounting to 3 to 18%. They increased with increasing temperature gap and amounted to 18% for a temperature gap of 236°. When the correct value $m = 0.477$ was used, the pairs of values agreed to within 2% whatever the temperature gap.

Three liquids namely acetic acid, acetone and diethylamine show some anomalous behaviour

immediately above their normal boiling points (concluding portions of the graphs at the right hand end, Fig. 1). In view of this situation, the low temperature data should also be examined right up to the melting point. Unfortunately these data are not readily available to us, except those of water. In this case the calculation of l_v at normal melting point gives 594.7 against observed 594.7.

The constants m and c are given in Table 2. They enable us to calculate l_v with the help of T_c absolutely. No comparison is involved. Incidentally, the plots of l_v against $(T_c - T)$ are not parabolas which require $m = 0.5$ which is approached only in the cases of *n*-propyl alcohol, acetone and diethylamine.

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